

TABLE: Significant Joule self-heating pervasive in the emergent thin-film transistor studies.V. Bruevich,^{1*} Y. Patel,² J. P. Singer,² and V. Podzorov^{1,*}¹ Dept. of Physics & Astronomy, Rutgers University, 136 Frelinghuysen Rd, Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA.² Dept. of Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering, Rutgers University, 98 Brett Road, Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA.

* E-mails: bruevich@physics.rutgers.edu, podzorov@physics.rutgers.edu

TABLE 1. Representative papers reporting the charge carrier mobility (μ) of field-effect transistors (FETs) based on metal-halide perovskites, conjugated polymers, and small-molecule organic semiconductors, reaching high apparent maximum power (W_{\max}) and power density (P_{\max}) in the transistor channel. Other parameters, including the channel width (W) and length (L), the effective source-drain electric field (E_{DS}), and the maximum source-drain current ($|I_{DS}|^{\max}$), are also listed together with the material and the corresponding Figure.

E_{DS} is the effective longitudinal (source-drain) electric field in the FET channel, applied during the recording of the transfer curve corresponding to the extracted W_{\max} and P_{\max} parameters, determined as $E_{DS} = |V_{DS}|/L$, where V_{DS} is the source-drain voltage.

W_{\max} is the maximum apparent electric power dissipated in the channel of the reported FET, calculated from the corresponding transfer curve as $W_{\max} = |I_{DS}|^{\max} \cdot |V_{DS}|$.

P_{\max} is the corresponding maximum electric power density emitted in the channel, calculated from the reported transfer curve as $P_{\max} = |I_{DS}|^{\max} \cdot |V_{DS}|/(LW)$.

For a control experiment emulating the experimental conditions in Ref. [1] and IR imaging of the corresponding sample's temperature distribution, see: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LPcXXPM58WQ>

Reference	semiconductor	Fig.	μ ($\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)	W (μm)	L (μm)	$ I_{DS} ^{\max}$ (A)	E_{DS} ($\text{kV}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$)	W_{\max} (W)	P_{\max} ($\text{W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$)*
H. Zhu <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nat. Electron.</i> (2023) ¹	Hybrid tin halide perovskite, $(\text{Cs}_x\text{FA}_{1-x})\text{PEA}_2\text{Sn}_8\text{I}_{25}$, $x = 10\%$	1c	72	1000	200	0.01	2	0.4	200
A. Liu <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nat. Electron.</i> (2022) ²	Tin halide perovskite, CsSnI_3	1d	55	1000	150	6.8×10^{-3}	2.67	0.272	181
W. Yang <i>et al.</i> , <i>Adv. Mater.</i> (2024) ³	Hybrid tin halide perovskite, FASnI_3 with F-PEAI	3i	56.1 (eff. ~ 30)	1000	100	9×10^{-3}	4	0.361	361
F. Yang <i>et al.</i> , <i>Org. Electron.</i> (2016) ⁴	Conj. polymer, P2MDPP2T-DTT	2c	5.27	1400	40	4.23×10^{-3}	25	0.423	755

* For comparison:

(a) The working surface of a typical household clothes iron emits about $0.36 \text{ W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ at full-power operation.(b) The integral power density emitted by the Sun at its surface is $\sim 6.4 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.(c) The power density of a CO_2 laser beam in industrial laser cutting machines for plastics, wood and leather is $3 - 10 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.

Reference	semiconductor	Fig.	μ ($\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)	W (μm)	L (μm)	$ I_{\text{DS}} ^{\text{max}}$ (A)	E_{DS} ($\text{kV}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$)	W_{max} (W)	P_{max} ($\text{W}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$)*
Y. Ji <i>et al.</i> , <i>Adv. Mater.</i> (2016) ⁵	Conj. polymer, PDPPMT-2T	2c	12.5	1400	40	4×10^{-3}	25	0.4	709
Y. Diao <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nat. Mater.</i> (2013) ⁶	Small mol., TIPS-pentacene	5b	8.1	1000	50	2×10^{-3}	20	0.2	400
A. Zhang <i>et al.</i> , <i>Macromol.</i> (2016) ⁷	Conj. polymer, PDPP4T-2M	3c	9.95	1400	50	2.8×10^{-3}	20	0.28	400
J. Mahmood <i>et al.</i> , <i>Adv. Mater.</i> (2021) ⁸	2D fused aromatic networks (43 nm-thick)	4c	996	4	0.5	1.55×10^{-3}	2	1.55×10^{-4}	7750
V. K. Bandari <i>et al.</i> , <i>Adv. Funct. Mater.</i> (2019) ⁹	Small mol., BTBT-T ₆	4b	34.6	5	4.4	6.7×10^{-5}	52.44	1.55×10^{-3}	7052
J. Liu <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nat. Commun.</i> (2015) ¹⁰	Small mol., 2,6-diphenylanthracene	3a	30	3.3	16.5	9.2×10^{-6}	36.36	0.55×10^{-3}	1000
H. Li <i>et al.</i> , <i>J. Am. Chem. Soc.</i> (2012) ¹¹	C ₆₀	4b	10.3	8.7	40	1.6×10^{-5}	25	1.6×10^{-3}	457
G. Giri <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nature</i> (2011) ¹²	Small mol., TIPS-pentacene	4c	4.59	1000	50	6.25×10^{-4}	20	62.5×10^{-3}	125
H. Iino <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nat. Commun.</i> (2015) ¹³	Small mol., Ph-BTBT-C ₁₀	3b	14.7	500	100	10^{-3}	10	0.1	200
H.-R. Tseng <i>et al.</i> , <i>Adv. Mater.</i> (2014) ¹⁴	Conj. polymer, PCDTPT	1c	23.7	1000	80	1.53×10^{-3}	10	0.122	153
C. Luo <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nano Lett.</i> (2014) ¹⁵	Conj. polymer, PCDTPT	4c	25.4	800	80	1.2×10^{-3}	10	0.096	150
J. Lee <i>et al.</i> , <i>J. Am. Chem. Soc.</i> (2013) ¹⁶	Conj. polymer, PTDPSe-SiC4	5d	5.97	1000	50	2.12×10^{-3}	20	0.212	424
H.-R. Tseng <i>et al.</i> , <i>Nano Lett.</i> (2012) ¹⁷	Conj. polymer, PCDTBT	3c	6.7	1000	20	6.4×10^{-3}	20	0.256	1280

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